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The effect of incentives on nurse performance at bahteramas general hospital, Indonesia

Amirullah ¹, Suhadi ^{2,*} and Nani Yuniar ²

¹ Master's Program in Public Health, Postgraduate Program at Halu Oleo University, Kendari, Indonesia.

² Public Health Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Halu Oleo University, Kendar, Indonesia.

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Abstract

Preliminary studies show that several programs have not reached the specified Minimum Service Standards (MSS), namely customer satisfaction in the Emergency Room (34.0%) from the standard 70%, outpatient satisfaction (73.21%) from the standard $\geq 90\%$, satisfaction of inpatients is 60.89% from the standard 90%. This type of research is quantitative research with a cross sectional study design. The population in this study amounted to 209 people, a sample of 138 respondents. The data were analyzed using the chi square test analysis. The results showed that there was a significant effect between incentives on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital ($0.000 < 0.05$). The conclusion in this study is that incentives affect the performance of nurses at Bahteramas General Hospital.

Keywords: Nurse; Incentive; Performance; Hospital

1. Introduction

Quality assurance in health care or *quality assurance in health care* is one approach or effort that is very important and fundamental in providing health services to patients. Health care professionals, both individuals and groups, must always strive to provide the best quality health services to all patients without exception [1]. Awareness of the importance of the existence of quality human resources, in this case nurses, needs to be followed up with various strategies that can improve the quality of nurses. One that is measured in the quality of nurse performance is the issue of discipline. Work discipline is a tool used by managers to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change an effort to increase one's awareness and willingness to obey all applicable social rules and norms. Factors that influence work discipline are goals and abilities, human relations, remuneration, justice, legal sanctions, leadership examples and firmness [2].

Nurses as one of the health workers in hospitals play an important role in achieving health development goals. The success of health services depends on the participation of nurses in providing quality care for patients [3]. Considering nurses as the most important resource in running the wheels of a hospital without underestimating the meaning of other human resources, nurses are required to have intellectual, interpersonal, technical and moral abilities. It aims to maintain and improve quality health services. Nursing provides services in hospitals 24 hours a day, and has constant contact with patients. Therefore, nursing services in hospitals are an integral part of health services. The contribution given by the nurse will determine the quality of service in the hospital. Thus, efforts to improve hospital services must be followed by efforts to improve the quality of nursing services [4].

One of the elements that has a big role and greatly determines the quality of hospital health services is nurses, this is because the nursing profession has a relatively large proportion, which is almost more than 50% of all hospital human

* Corresponding author: Suhadi

Public Health Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Halu Oleo University, Kendari, Indonesia.

resources and most interact directly with patients. More work and duties than other staff, because the nature and function of this workforce is to support medical services in the form of nursing services known as nursing care [5]. Attention to improving the performance of nurses in providing nursing services in hospitals is a very basic demand, because these factors can shape the performance of nurses in hospitals so as to support the implementation of their duties and responsibilities in providing nursing services. If this is not getting enough attention and left without proper handling efforts, it is feared that it will have an impact on the success of improving the quality of health personnel resources, especially in providing nursing services in hospitals [4].

The Regional General Hospital (RGH) Bahteramas, which is located in Baruga District, Kendari City, belongs to the Regional Government of Southeast Sulawesi Province which functions as a referral center in the Southeast Sulawesi Province. Treatment bed facilities in 2016 amounted to 316 beds, in 2017 there were 425 beds, in 2018 there were 457 beds, in 2019 there were 456 beds and in 2020 there were 450 beds. Hospital performance is measured by the occupancy rate of *Bed Occupancy Rate* (BOR), with the average BOR in 2016 amounting to 58.51%, in 2017 amounting to 58.16%, in 2018 amounting to 58.49%, in 2019 amounting to 56.02 % and in 2020 amounted to 37.12%. Based on the ideal standard for the hospital BOR value is the range of 60%-80% [6]. The number of patient visits at Bahteramas Hospital for outpatient in 2016 was 129,359 patients, in 2017 there were 153,049 patients, in 2018 there were 159,215 patients, in 2019 there were 133,496 patients and in 2020 there were 90,227. In-patient visits in 2016 were 12,109, in 2017 there were 13,441 patients, in 2018 there were 15,793 patients, in 2019 there were 17,859 patients and in 2020 there were 10,120 patients [6].

The results of interviews with patients at Bahteramas General Hospital showed that the officers on duty were not clear in explaining the administrative process that should be carried out so that the patient and the patient's family had difficulty dealing, the lack of explanation of the cost difference for each action, especially if the patient from class III moved to class II, the officer did not respond to every complaint submitted by the patient, every family who contacted the officer was responded to leave first and the officer would follow, but it still takes a relatively long time to meet the patient. Based on the results of initial observations, it was found that there were problems that were often found by some nurses who lacked a high commitment, namely officers who often came late and were sometimes less friendly to patients or even patients' families. Then officers tend to be unable to complete the tasks given by their superiors properly and on time. This is due to the lack of interaction between superiors and subordinates, such as providing guidance, motivational encouragement to all members to achieve goals. In addition, officers complain about the incentives they receive because the amount received is not large but there are still frequent arrears in payments, which in turn causes the performance and commitment of officers to be low.

Bahteramas's status as a referral centre makes Bahteramas RGH, must always be alert in accepting the number of patient visits at any time, Bahteramas RGH is required to provide truly optimal and quality services. To achieve this, resources are needed which of course must also have an optimal amount of quality to provide quality services as well. Based on data on the achievement of minimum service standards at Bahteramas Hospital, it shows that several programs that have not reached the specified Minimum Service Standards (MSS) are customer satisfaction in the Emergency Room (34.0%) from the standard 70%, outpatient satisfaction (73.21 %) from the standard 90%, inpatient satisfaction 60.89% from the standard 90% [6]. Thus, based on data showing that at Bahteramas Hospital there are still several MSS such as emergency customer satisfaction, outpatient satisfaction, and inpatient satisfaction that are not in accordance with standards, it means that employee performance has not been carried out optimally in accordance with predetermined standards. The purpose of this study is to analysis the effect of incentives, discipline, supervision on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas Regional General Hospital

2. Material and methods

This research was carried out at the Bahteramas Regional General Hospital in June 2022. The design of this study was a quantitative study with a *cross sectional approach*, where the researcher observed or measured variables at a certain time. The population in this study were all nurses in the inpatient room at Bahteramas Hospital, which amounted to 209 people. The sample size in this study was 138 respondents. This study uses primary data and secondary data from all nurses at Bahteramas General Hospital. The data were analyzed using univariate and bivariate analysis.

3. Results

3.1. Univariate Analysis

3.1.1. Incentive

Adequate incentives will encourage employee morale and passion, so that employees will continue to maintain and improve their work, eventually increasing profits in achieving the goals and objectives set, so that agencies and employees are expected to be more *solid* in building togetherness towards the progress of the company/institution.

Table 1 Distribution of respondents based on incentives at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province

No	Incentive	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Enough	93	67.4
2.	Not enough	45	32.6
Total		138	100

Source: Primary Data in 2022

Table 1 shows that the distribution of respondents based on the assessment of incentives in the sufficient category amounted to 93 people (67.4%) and the less category 45 people (32.6%).

3.1.2. Performance

Table 2 Distribution of respondents based on the performance of nurses at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province

No	Nurse Performance	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Enough	94	68.1
2	Not enough	44	31.9
Total		138	100

Source: Primary Data in 2022

Table 2 shows that the distribution of respondents' performance based on the sufficient category amounted to 94 people (68.1 %) and the less category amounted to 44 people (31.9 %)

3.2. Bivariate Analysis

The Effect of Incentives on Nurse Performance at Bahteramas General Hospital can be presented in table 3:

Table 3 Distribution of respondents based on the performance of nurses at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province

Incentive	Nurse Performance				Total		P
	Enough		Not enough		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Enough	74	53.6	19	13.8	93	67.4	0.000
Not enough	20	14.5	25	18.1	45	32.6	
Total	94	68.1	44	31.9	138	100	

Source: Primary Data in 2022

Table 3 shows that of the 93 respondents (67.4%) who stated that the incentives were sufficient, there were more nurses who had sufficient performance, namely 74 respondents (53.6%) than nurses who had less performance, namely 19 respondents (13.8%). Meanwhile, from 45 respondents (32.6%) who stated that incentives were lacking, there were 20 respondents (14.5%) who had sufficient performance and as many as 25 respondents (18.1%) who had poor performance.

The results of the chi square test obtained that the value of $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$) means that H_0 is rejected. This shows that there is an effect of incentives on the performance of nurses at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Effect of Incentives on Nurse Performance at Bahteramas General Hospital

Incentives if planned and implemented properly can stimulate employee morale and responsibility for the work done. Incentive enough to motivate employees to excel. The results showed that there were 19 respondents (13.8%) who said the incentives received were quite good but performance was still lacking. This can happen because it is influenced by other factors such as the respondent is a new employee so they still need guidance and direction, the lack of good supervision of the head of the room, and the respondent's lack of knowledge about the main tasks that must be done so that performance is not optimal.

In addition, there were 20 respondents who said the incentives received were lacking but still had good performance. This can happen because of the strong will or commitment of the respondent himself who must make him work hard, the respondent's knowledge related to his main duties as a nurse, and the relationships between colleagues that are well established to make a person motivated to work well.

The results showed that there was a significant effect between incentives on the performance of nurses at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Fitria, Sawitri 2017 which states that there is a positive and significant effect of incentives on nurse job satisfaction. This means that the better and the higher the incentives received by the nurses, the higher the job satisfaction of the nurses [7]. However, the provision of incentives according to Mardalela 2018 that incentives can be shown through non - *financial incentives*, is an incentive *which* is usually a psychological reward. While the forms are, among others: Fostering a sense of pride and pleasure towards employees, giving sympathy and fair treatment to employees, providing opportunities to be promoted, equal opportunities to receive training, security and peace of mind at work, as well as expectations for awards, welfare adequate coverage including family medical treatment, old age benefits, accident insurance and others [8]. Research conducted by [9] which shows that there is a relationship between the provision of incentives and the performance of nurses. Nurses as health workers who have the main responsibility in nursing services and are often a barometer of the good and bad of a health service in hospitals, especially those who are hospitalized, nurses are required to work professionally and intensely.

The results of filling out the incentive questionnaire show that the statement item No. 1 (the incentives/bonuses given are actually given to officers who carry out their duties as expected) are answered according to the most, namely as much as 81%, statement item No. 2 (Amount of incentives provided) accepted according to your current position) answered according to 69%, statement item No. 3 (The amount of incentives in your unit is in accordance with other units in the hospital) answered according to 61%, statement item No. 4 (Incentives received are very helpful in meeting all your basic needs) answered according to 61%, statement item No. 5 (Relationship of incentives with work spirit) was answered according to 60%, statement item No. 6 (Available incentives are useful for officers) answered according to 60%, statement No. 7 (The amount of incentives received is in accordance with the regional minimum wage determined by the government) answered according to 60%, statement No.8 (Incentives and work environment atmosphere can always be foster employee morale in work) by 58%, statement No. 9 (Hospital management needs to consider providing incentives in the form of vacation packages to nurses) was answered accordingly by 58% and statement no. 10 (Giving incentives creates favorable conditions for management and nurses in increase work productivity) answered accordingly by 61%. So it can be concluded that there are still many statement items that get answers that are not appropriate. According to the researcher's assumptions, everyone has a different assessment of something, including the provision of incentives. A person can judge that the incentive he receives is high, but in the judgment of others, the incentive is still low for him. This can be influenced by the needs of life so that everyone's assessment is different. And there is injustice in the distribution of incentives.

Nursing services are provided to patients in the form of nurse performance and must be based on high abilities. Performance is the result of a person's work carried out in accordance with his duties in an organization. In assessing the performance of nurses, standards of nursing practice are used as a guide for nurses in carrying out nursing care. Evaluation instrument for the application of nursing care standards in nursing care documentation study guidelines which include assessment, diagnosis, planning, action, evaluation and nursing care records.

Providing incentives can increase the motivation of nurses to improve performance. Motivation is an influential drive to generate, direct, and maintain behavior related to the work environment. The higher work motivation makes nurses have a high spirit to provide the best service. Nurses need to be given remuneration in the form of salary, compensation and incentives. With the provision of these incentives will increase the interest of nurses in providing nursing care, including the completeness of documentation of nursing care. Based on the theory and data obtained, the higher the incentives received by nurses, the more complete the nursing care carried out by nurses. Vice versa, the lower the incentives received by nurses, the less their performance in carrying out their duties and functions as nurses [8].

This is in accordance with the condition of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital who showed good performance during work. Incentives have an effect on work motivation which is indicated by good performance. So, the more perceived incentives are good, it will be in line with the nurse's performance. However, there are also respondents who show that the performance of nurses is lacking, and this is in line with the statement that the incentives received are felt to be lacking. According to Pangabean (2017), suggests that incentives are direct rewards paid to employees because performance exceeds the specified standard. Assuming that money can encourage employees to work even harder, those who are productive prefer their salaries to be paid based on the results of their work. Therefore, the provision of incentives can stimulate or encourage officers so that in them there is a greater enthusiasm for achievement for improving performance. Incentive pay encourages employees to work better because there is a direct relationship between the performance performed and the results obtained. Money can actually be a motivator [10]. As shown by people who work hard hours that they don't really enjoy. Giving salaries that are not in accordance with the wishes of employees or giving salaries that are not sufficient for the needs of employees can cause financial worries in employees, causing stress that is off the job, which of course will affect work motivation and productivity.

This illustrates that the role of the workplace here is very important to maintain a high level of motivation and even better if it can increase the motivation of nurses. How the hospital provides an incentive system that is more motivating will also be able to encourage nurses to further improve their performance, such as punctuality when giving incentives to nurses, needs that can be met, and being able to contribute to short-term benefits and build nurse motivation for long-term success. long for both the hospital and for nurses.

In this study, there were respondents who assumed their incentives were sufficient but there were respondents whose performance was lacking, while the respondents who assumed their incentives were lacking were respondents who performed well. This can happen due to several reasons or external factors that can influence so that it can happen and it could also be because the relationship between superiors and subordinates will affect the activities carried out daily. Based on this description, it is known that incentives are a contributing factor to employee performance. For this reason, it is necessary for hospitals to pay attention to employee welfare through incentives. Hospitals and employees need to sit together with the Health Office to discuss and evaluate periodically the amount of incentives that will be received by each employee on the condition that they provide the best performance.

5. Conclusion

The conclusion in this study is that there is a significant influence between incentives on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital. Suggestions are expected to Bahteramas Hospital to be able to regulate the system of providing incentives that are in accordance with standards and involve employees, especially nurses, to be able to determine the standard of providing incentives so that nurses will know the maximum effort required to work in order to get the expected incentives .

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors in the making of this scientific article have no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

All informants/respondents involved in this study have stated their consent as informants/respondents to be interviewed and provided information/information in accordance with research needs.

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